

Population dynamics of oriental leaf worm
Spodoptera litura on Chrysanthemum

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ABSTRACT

The study on seasonal incidence of oriental leaf worm, *Spodoptera litura* (Fabricius) in Chrysanthemum was carried out at Pune Maharashtra during *Kharif* 2024-25. Plant infestation started at a low rate of 6.67 per cent during the 33rd Standard Meteorological Week (SMW) and gradually increased, reaching its highest level of 48.89 per cent by the 42nd SMW. This peak infestation was associated with weather parameters including a maximum temperature of 32.6°C, a minimum temperature of 23°C, morning and evening relative humidity levels of 92 % and 58 %, respectively. After this peak, the infestation steadily declined and reached to a minimum level of 8.89 per cent infestation during 50th SMW. Correlation analysis revealed a highly significant positive correlation was found between infestation caused by *S. litura* and maximum temperature ($r = 0.692^{***}$), significant positive correlation with sunshine hours ($r = 0.446^*$). It showed significant but negative correlation with evening relative humidity ($r = -0.447^*$).

Keywords: Chrysanthemum, *Spodoptera litura*, seasonal incidence, abiotic factors, correlation.

INTRODUCTION

Chrysanthemum is cultivated for loose flowers, cut flowers, as potted plants and border plants in the garden in India. Chrysanthemum production is impacted by several issues, but the most significant one is insect pest damage from aphids, caterpillars, mites, whiteflies, thrips and leaf miners. The oriental leaf worm, *Spodoptera litura* (Fabricius) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is another foliage feeder that results in significant economic losses.

The oriental leaf worm, *S. litura* is economically significant and polyphagous pests on the horticultural and field crops and commonly referred as a tobacco leaf eating caterpillar. It is commonly distributed throughout Asia, which includes China, Korea, Japan, India and Pakistan (Cheng et al. 2017). In recent years, oriental leaf worm has been causing significant losses to ornamental crops in India as well as in Maharashtra. The population dynamics of this pest was carried out many other field as well as horticultural crops but it is essential to study the same in Chrysanthemum horti-ecosystem for its effective management

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A study on the seasonal incidence of the oriental leaf worm, *Spodoptera litura* infesting chrysanthemum was conducted at the Directorate of Floricultural Research, Mundhava, Pune, Maharashtra, during the *Kharif* season of 2024–25. The chrysanthemum variety *Purnima Local White* was transplanted in 9 m × 6.6 m plot and at row-to-row distance of 90 cm and plant to plant distance of 30 cm. The experimental plot was maintained without any insecticidal application throughout the season. The observations on seasonal incidence

of *S. litura* in chrysanthemum were taken at weekly intervals, starting 15 days after transplanting (DAT) and continuing till the senescence of the first flower flush. The number of infested plants due to *S. litura* was counted from randomly selected 45 plants and per cent plant infestation was calculated. Per cent plant infestation was calculated by using formula:

Per cent plant infestation

$$\frac{\text{Number of infested plants}}{\text{Total number of plants}} \times 100$$

The data on per cent plant infestation due to *S. litura* were correlated with meteorological parameters

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data on per cent plant infestation in chrysanthemum due to *S. litura* was recorded weekly from the 31st Standard Meteorological Week (SMW) (30 July–5 August) to the 50th SMW (10 December–16 December) and is presented in Fig. 1. Initiation of damage was observed during the 33rd SMW (6.67 %), which steadily increased and reached its peak during the 42nd SMW (48.89%).

At this peak, the maximum and minimum temperatures were 32.6°C and 23°C while morning and evening relative humidity were 92% and 58%, respectively.

Rainfall during this period was 26.9 mm received through two rainy days, with a wind speed of 2.7 km/h and 5.8 hours of bright sunshine. Following this peak, the plant infestation gradually decreased, reaching 8.89 percent during the 50th SMW.

Fig.1: Seasonal incidence of *Spodoptera litura*(Fabricius) on chrysanthemum during *Kharif* 2024-25

The correlation coefficient (Table 2) between per cent plant infestation and various weather parameters was calculated for the period from the 31st SMW (30th July to 5th August) to the 50th SMW (10th December to 16th December). The results are presented in Fig 2.

Table 2. Correlation of weather parameters and per cent plant infestation due to *Spodoptera litura*(Fabricius) on chrysanthemum during *Kharif* 2024-25.

Weather parameters	Correlation coefficient (r)
T _{max} (°C)	0.692***
T _{min} (°C)	-0.019
RH I (%)	0.227
RH II (%)	-0.447*
Rainfall (mm)	-0.255
Rainy days	-0.403
Wind speed (km/hr)	-0.437
Bright sunshine hours	0.446*

NS= non- significant

*Significant at 0.05 level (r= ±0.444)

***Significant at 0.001 level (r= ±0.679)

There was highly significant positive correlation of *S. litura* infestation with maximum temperature (r = 0.692***). A significant positive correlation of *S. litura* was observed with bright sunshine hours (r = 0.446*), while a significant negative correlation was recorded with evening relative humidity (r = -0.447*). However, non-significant negative correlations were found with minimum temperature (r = -0.019^{NS}), rainfall (r = -0.255^{NS}), number of rainy days (r = -0.403^{NS}) and wind speed (r = -0.437^{NS}). Morning relative humidity showed a positive but non-significant correlation (r = 0.227^{NS}) with *S. litura* infestation.

The seasonal incidence of *S. litura* was studied by earlier research workers on capsicum, groundnut, soybean, etc. But no research findings are available related to seasonal incidence of *S. litura* on chrysanthemum to support the current results. However, Tompe *et al.* (2020) reported initial incidence of *S. litura* on capsicum (fruit

infestation %) under polyhouse condition noticed in 30th SMW and reported non-significant negative correlation with minimum temperature

Similarly, the correlation results of current experiment are in line with the results of Nayak *et al.* (2019), who found a highly significant positive correlation of *S. litura* with maximum temperature, significant positive relation with sun shine hours, significant negative with evening relative humidity and non-significant negative correlation between minimum temperature, rainfall, wind speed

and *S. litura* in groundnut similarly Bangale *et al.* (2019) found non-significant negative correlation of *S. litura* with minimum temperature, rainfall and rainy days, while positive but non-significant with morning relative humidity in soybean crop. These results from different agro-ecosystems were in line with the current finding. This indicates that bright sunny days after the rainy and the dry spell in rainy season make the congenial conditions for the aggravation of the *S. litura* in chrysanthemum crop.

Fig.2: Correlation coefficient between weather parameters and plant infestation due to *Spodoptera litura* (Fabricius)

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